

Integrated nematode management practices in various crops in Haryana

Rubal Kamboj*, Vinod Kumar, Sardul Singh Mann and Deepak Kumar

Department of Nematology, CCS HAU, Hisar-125004

Plant parasitic nematodes (PPNs) are hidden enemies of crops and are one of the many groups of harmful organisms which depend on plants for their survival. PPNs cause damage to almost all crops, however, due to their subterranean habit, microscopic size (0.3 to 10 mm length), they are invisible with the naked eye. PPNs have been described, characterized on the basis of their feeding habits *i.e.*, plant feeders, bacterial feeders, fungal feeders, algal feeders, animal predators and omnivores. PPNs not only cause damage individually but form disease-complexes with other micro-organism like fungi and bacteria. PPNs with high population density cause economically significant yield reduction in most agricultural crops. In Haryana an estimated average loss is 20-25% due to these tiny organisms. In the recent surveys it has been observed that more than 50% of the polyhouses of Haryana are infested with root-knot nematodes. Changes in agricultural conditions have a significant impact on the emergence of new nematode problems in Haryana. Damage is greater in vegetable and horticultural crops than in cereal crops. Nematode symptoms are similar to those of other pathogens and abiotic diseases such as a lack of water and nutrients.

New problems identified in Haryana

- Root-knot nematode, *Meloidogyne graminicola* has been continuously increasing in traditional as well as non-traditional rice growing areas of the state.
- Guava orchards in Haryana have been found heavily infested with root-knot and root-rot complex disease.
- Root-knot nematode, *Meloidogyne* spp. problem has been increasing tremendously under protected cultivation.

Plant Responses to Nematode Infection

Plants react differently to nematode infections depending on cultivar and species. The damage levels are also affected by temperature, soil moisture content, nematode type, soil characteristics, and crop

rotations. Premature wilting, chlorosis, nutrient deficiency leading to stunted growth, fragile roots, and swollen root areas due to gall formation are some of the most common and unusual plant symptoms. Infected plant roots undergo discoloration, and become stubby and stunted, making the plant susceptible to water stress conditions. Reduction in crop yield is often monitored as a sign of nematode infestation, both in terms of quality and quantity. General above ground symptoms of nematodes damage are-stunted plant growth in patches, yellowing of foliage, wilting, poor tillering in field/annual crops; and dieback, defoliation type of symptoms in perennial crops, most of them resembling nutrient deficiency symptoms (Fig.1). The below-ground symptoms include galls or knots on the roots of crops. These galls vary in size from pin-head to large size which in case of heavy infection may coalesce to form large secondary galls. Gall shape and size depend on *Meloidogyne* spp. and host crop, sometimes many galls and produce compound gall.

Fig.1. Symptoms produce by root knot nematodes in tomato A) Above-ground B) Below-ground

Causes of an increase in nematodes problem in Haryana

- ❖ Even low nematode populations can cause damage when they are associated with other fungi and bacteria.
- ❖ Nematode management here must be considered primarily as exclusion or avoidance.
- ❖ Once nematodes are introduced it is difficult to manage them.
- ❖ Continuous growing of same crop year after year increases nematode population in the soil.
- ❖ Lack of nematode management interventions and most importantly lack of technical knowledge among farmers.

Source of nematodes infection and spread

- ❖ Infested soil

- ❖ Infected planting material
- ❖ Water
- ❖ Seed
- ❖ Implements used in polyhouses
- ❖ Footwear of workers
- ❖ Agricultural machinery

Major nematodes problem encountered in Haryana and their recommendations

The development of new methods to control such nematodes is of major importance because the chemical nematicides are associated with environmental and health concerns. An alternative approach to manage PPNs is the using of their natural enemies. Among them, the nematode destroying fungi, comprising a group of soil-living fungi, natural enemies of PPNs are of significant importance. Use of nematode destroying fungi as bio-control agent either alone or integrated with other nematode management strategies offer an environmentally sustainable method. For the management of nematode problems preventive measures can be taken up to keep the population of PPNs below economic threshold level. With the increasing concern on environment, various alternative pest control methods like cultural, physical and biological control methods and botanicals are being tried to reduce the nematode damage of crops. However, judicious use of chemical nematicides could be applied for protection of many crops. Therefore, current options for nematode management are cultural practices, physical methods, bio-intensive nematode suppression, botanicals and sensible use of chemical nematicides.

Recommendations generated for field applications

Crop	Nematode Disease/Nematodes	Recommendations
Wheat	Earcockle & tundu	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Water flotation and salt sedimentation of contaminated seeds: Remove the floating galls with a sieve, dry healthy seeds in shade before sowing.
Wheat, barley	Molya	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Two to three deep ploughings during May/June at 10-15 days' interval. ● Rotation of wheat/barley with mustard or gram for 1-2 years. ● Grow resistant barley var. C 164, BH 75/wheat Raj MR-1. ● Early sowing of wheat (up to 15th November) ● In heavy infestation, application of carbofuran (Furadan 3G) @ 33Kg/ha at sowing. ● Seed treatment with <i>Azotobacter chroococcum</i> HT-54 (Azotica) @ 200 ml/40 kg of seed. Dry in shade. ● In cereal cyst nematode (Molya disease) infested areas of south western districts of Haryana, to reduce the damage of cyst nematode, sow the wheat crop in dry condition and apply irrigation immediately.

Rice	Rice root nematode	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Application of carbofuran (Furadan 3G) @ 33Kg/ha at nursery sowing
	Root-knot nematode	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For the management of rice root-knot nematode in rice nursery, soil solarise the nursery beds before sowing for 15 days during summer. Cover the nursery beds with transparent polythene sheet (25-micron thickness) after light irrigation. Cover the edges of polythene sheet with soil to make it air tight.
Tomato, brinjal, okra	Root-knot nematodes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two to three deep ploughings during May/June at 10-15 days' interval. Application of carbofuran (Furadan 3G) @ 33Kg/ha at nursery sowing. Grow root-knot nematode resistant variety- Hisar Lalit of tomato. In okra through soil application of <i>Trichoderma viride</i> @ 2.5 kg/ha at the time of sowing. In tomato by using neem cake @ 750 g per m² in nursery beds.
Citrus	Slow decline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Application of carbofuran (Furadan 3G) @ 13 g/sq.m.(about 9 sq. m. around a plant) just before flowering, pulverize the soil in the basin area and mix the chemical thoroughly followed by flood irrigation. Application of carbofuran (Furadan 3G) @ 7 g/sq.m. + neem cake @ 1Kg (about 9 sq. m. around a plant) just before flowering; pulverize the soil in the basin area and mix the chemical thoroughly followed by flood irrigation.
Grapes	Root-knot nematodes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Application of carbofuran (Furadan 3G) @ 13 g/sq.m. (about 9 sq. m. around a plant) just before flowering; pulverize the soil in the basin area and mix the chemical thoroughly followed by flood irrigation. Application of carbofuran (Furadan 3G) @ 7g/sq. m. in combination with garlic as intercrop in between vine rows.
Button mushroom	<i>Aphelenchoides</i> spp.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply 4% (w/v) neem seed kernel extract (NSKE) at spawning @ 7.5 litre per q compost as prophylactic measure.
Cotton	<i>Meloidogyne incognita</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Seed treatment with <i>Gluconacetobacter diazotrophicus</i> strain 35-47 (Biotica) @ 50 ml per 5 kg seed. Dry in shade.
Bottlegourd	<i>Meloidogyne</i> spp.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Application of neem cake @ 30g/spot + seed treatment with <i>Gluconacetobacter diazotrophicus</i> strain 35-47 @ 50ml/2kg seed.
Protected Cultivation system	<i>Meloidogyne</i> spp.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil solarization by 2-3 deep summer ploughings in the month of May-June at 15 days interval followed by light irrigation and covering of soil with 25-micron transparent polythene sheet for 30 days during June-July in Polyhouses. Soil application of <i>Trichoderma viride</i> @ 20g/m², mixed with neem cake/FYM/Vermicompost @ 100g/m² in the tomato beds. Management of root-knot nematode in polyhouse grown capsicum apply neem cake @ 200 g/m² in beds, fifteen days prior to transplanting. For the management of root-knot nematode in polyhouse grown capsicum apply neem cake @ 200g/m² in beds, fifteen days prior to transplanting.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none">● For the management of root-knot nematode in the cucumber in polyhouse, take the following measures.<ol style="list-style-type: none">i) Remove and destroy the plants of the previous crop along with the roots.ii) Solarise the soil during summer by covering it with a 25µm thick transparent polythene sheet for 15-20 days, after light irrigation. Cover the edges of polythene sheet with soil to make it air tight.iii) Add FYM enriched with fungus (<i>Purpureocillium lilacinum</i>) @ of 1 kg/m² in the soil. For preparing enriched FYM, mix 2 kg of fungus in 1 ton of FYM. Cover it with polythene sheet after sprinkling with water. After 10-15 days, mix it well on the paved surface.
--	--	---

